

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

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DISTANCE LEARNING OPPORTUNITIES IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. *In today's interconnected world, the demand for language learning is growing. The purpose of this article is to analyze a variety of e-learning advantages in the language acquisition. In addition, it explores the teaching methodology and potential barriers associated with distance language learning.*

Keywords: *Distance learning, language acquisition, online courses, virtual classrooms, technology, immersive experiences, global connectivity, remote learning, intercultural competence, linguistic proficiency.*

Language acquisition is a complex process influenced by various factors, including instructional methods, learner motivation, and environmental context (Krashen, 1982; Long, 1990). The conventional methods such as classroom-based teaching have been dominant for a long time. However, the global development of technology and social media has revolutionized the way the language is acquired.

Distance learning, defined as the delivery of instruction to learners who are separated from the instructor by time and/or location, has emerged as a viable alternative to traditional classroom-based instruction (Simonson et al., 2012). Distance learning offers several advantages, including flexibility, accessibility, and the ability to accommodate diverse learner needs and preferences (Moore & Kearsley, 2012). In the past several years, due to the pandemic and the availability of social media platforms, online education has gained popularity among all age, gender and social groups since the rising number of students are choosing virtual classroom instead the traditional classroom.

In the light of these considerations, the integration of online learning into language learning can offer a variety of platforms and technological advancements, including virtual classroom, online courses and mobile applications and immersive language learning experience. Each platform has its unique features which can be suitable to different type of learners, considering their preferences and learning styles. Nowadays, the state-of-the-art virtual classroom facilitate the real-time interactions

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between learners and a teacher while the mobile apps provide ongoing access to materials used for language learning.

As for the methodology of distance language learning, a wide range of methods are utilized ranging from self-paced learning to instructor-based learning. It is also worth mentioning that blended learning interacting face-to-face learning with e-learning is currently gaining popularity. Adaptive learning algorithms provide a more efficient and immersive language learning opportunities, taking into account several factors such as the age, preferences, gender, culture and others.

The remote learning can offer several opportunities over the classroom-based learning. Firstly, it provides flexibility owing to the fact that regardless of location and time students can have access to online courses and study at their own pace and convenience. Additionally, online language learning offers a diverse range of online language courses and resources which may not be available in the local settings. What's more, online learning tends to be more immersive and interactive since it incorporates multimedia resources and interactive exercises, promoting active engagement of students.

In spite of the growing popularity of distance learning in language learning, there are some questions in terms of efficiency of virtual language learning compared to the face-to-face classroom. While some studies have reported positive outcomes associated with distance learning, others have raised concerns about its ability to facilitate meaningful language acquisition (Golonka et al., 2014). Furthermore, external factors including the learners' character, preference and technological infrastructure have a huge impact on the effectiveness of online language learning. It also shows some disadvantages such as technological problems, lack of face-to-face interaction and potential feelings of isolation among learners. Moreover, making sure the quality and credibility of online courses is essential to earn learners trust and satisfaction.

Distance learning offers unprecedented opportunities for language learning, providing flexibility, accessibility, and creative learning experiences. By interacting technology and pedagogical strategies, teachers can enhance the effectiveness of distance language learning and reach a broader audience of learners. Ongoing research and interaction are crucial to be aware the full potential of distance learning in language education.

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